

NONLINEAR MECHANICAL BEHAVIOR OF THERMOPLASTIC
MATRIX MATERIALS FOR ADVANCED COMPOSITES

R. J. Arenz
(Gonzaga University, Spokane, WA 99258, USA)
R. F. Landel
(Jet Propulsion Laboratory, Pasadena, CA 91103, USA)

ABSTRACT

As even small strains can produce nonlinear effects in thermoplastic polymers used as the matrix of advanced composite materials, there is a growing need to study the nonlinear viscoelastic mechanical behavior of glassy polymers. The analysis of the interaction between the matrix and the reinforcing fibers may be different from those with thermosetting plastics; in addition such behavior greatly influences the processing conditions to be used during the manufacturing cycle of composites. Two recent theories of nonlinear mechanical response are quantitatively compared and related to experimental data. Computer techniques are formulated to handle the numerical integration and iterative procedures needed to solve the associated sets of coupled nonlinear differential equations. Problems encountered during these formulations are discussed and some open questions described. Bearing in mind these cautions, the consequences of changing parameters that appear in the formulations on the resulting engineering properties are discussed. Hence, engineering approaches to the analysis of thermoplastic matrix material can be suggested.

INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic polymers are beginning to be used in place of thermosets as the matrix of composite materials to provide higher toughness and facilitate manufacturing. As these glassy polymers can exhibit nonlinear effects at relatively small strains, there is need to assess their mechanical behavior in the nonlinear regime to account for possible interactions between the matrix and reinforcing fibers of composites and to properly specify processing conditions for their manufacture. A necessary preliminary step is the complete characterization of the nonlinear mechanical behavior of the glassy polymers themselves, ideally involving both elastic and viscoelastic nonlinearities.

Of the various nonlinear theories proposed in recent years, the approaches of Knauss and Emri¹ and Shay and Caruthers² have been chosen for quantitative study as they relate closely to the physics of the material and give promise of direct engineering application. They treat the phenomena of mechanical stress relaxation and creep and are based on the concept of free volume at temperatures below the glass transition temperature (T_g). The free volume is the internal space available for chain movement and relaxation to take place as the material tends toward the equilibrium state of maximum density (no "hole" of free volume). Viscoelastic time dependency is accounted for by suitable time-scale shifting factors (analogous to the well-known time-temperature thermodynamic shift). The stress state can in principle be related to free volume since a mechanically-induced dilatation tends to increase the free volume.

THE KNAUSS-EMRI APPROACH

Knauss and Emri¹ postulate that the free volume reflects not only temperature and stress-induced dilatation but also a swelling due to solvent content. They assume that

the changes in free volume due to any of these variables are simply additive with the operative parameter being the total fractional free volume written as

$$f = f_0 + A[\alpha(t) * (dT)] + B[M(t) * d\tau_{kk}] + C[\gamma(t) * (dc)] \quad (1)$$

where f_0 is the fractional free volume at a reference temperature, A,B,C are material parameters (assumed constant), α is the thermal volume expansion coefficient, T is the temperature, M is the linear viscoelastic bulk creep compliance, τ_{kk} is the first stress invariant ($\tau_{11} + \tau_{22} + \tau_{33}$), γ is the solvent-related volume creep function, and c is the solvent concentration. The "*" indicates Stieltjes convolution (superposition integral).

Formulation in terms of tensor stress and strain components enables the theory to embrace quite general deformation states. The authors take up the uniaxial extension case for inputs of constant strain (relaxation) and constant strain rate. A typical set of relations (for the case of constant strain rate ($\dot{\epsilon}_0$) with no solvent content) may be written as

$$\tau_{11}(t) = \dot{\epsilon}_0 \int_0^t E(t' - \xi') d\xi \quad (2)$$

$$t' - \xi' = \int_{\xi}^t \frac{d\xi}{a[T, \theta(\xi)]} \quad (3)$$

$$\log a(t) = \frac{-b}{2.3f_0} \left[\frac{B \theta(t) + \alpha \Delta T}{f_0 + B \theta(t) + \alpha \Delta T} \right] \quad (4)$$

$$3 \theta(t) = (M_0 + M_1) \tau_{11}(t) - M_1 \int_0^t \exp\left[-\left(\frac{t' - \xi'}{\tau}\right)\right] \frac{\partial \tau_{11}}{\partial \xi} d\xi \quad (5)$$

where θ is the stress-induced dilatation, E is the linear viscoelastic tensile relaxation modulus, b is a material constant, τ_{11} is the uniaxial tensile stress, t and t' are actual and "reduced" time, respectively, ΔT is the difference in temperature from some chosen reference temperature (at which the linear material properties were determined). Eq. (4) is the WLF-Doolittle shift factor relation and Eq. (5) represents the bulk compliance M as a standard linear solid with the single retardation time τ .

The authors present comparisons of their numerical solutions of the theoretical equations with experimental results that appear to offer good correlation, including stress relaxation and both loading and unloading constant strain rate processes. Other situations to which they apply the method are pressure aging with subsequent straining and volume change from quenching or sudden heating. All comparisons with straining experiments are limited to temperatures close to T_g , so applicability remote from T_g remains a question.

Several experimentally-determined material parameters for poly (vinyl acetate), PVAc, are given¹ for use in Eq. (4), but the bulk time-dependent behavior of PVAc is less satisfactorily defined. Their application of the method makes evaluation of bulk behavior a part of the solution technique in somewhat of a trial and error fashion. The set of nonlinear equations appropriate for a uniaxial stress relaxation process were applied to experimental data at finite strain levels of 0.01, 0.03, and 0.05 as shown in master relaxation modulus (E(t)) curves, duplicated here as curves B, C, D of Fig. 1. (Unfortunately, no reference temperature was given.) Their analytical reduction to the zero (or infinitesimal) strain relaxation curve A involved the representation of bulk compliance M(t) as a standard linear solid material. However, the bulk parameter listings of Ref. 1 appear to be off by an order of magnitude from published results for PVAc³ and they are contradictory to values given by the authors in a later publication⁴ of the theory.

To resolve this uncertainty and further assess the consistency, range of applicability and ease of computation for engineering use of the method, we developed the additional

mathematics needed to solve for numerical results. As with most other nonlinear viscoelastic theories, the Knauss-Emri formulation requires step-wise time-incremented solutions of the coupled nonlinear partial differential equations; this involves numerical integration accompanied by iteration to determine the "reduced" (material) time associated with each step.

We have focused our attention on the stress response to uniaxial constant strain and constant strain rate processes. FORTRAN computer programs have been written and run on a VAX 11/785 mainframe computer. To enable realistic wide-band material property representation, Prony series of decaying exponential terms were used throughout to evaluate relaxation moduli.

To set up computer programs, Eq. (2) to (5) (or an analogous set for the relaxation process) were recast in numerical integration form as summations for the appropriate time step to determine a stress or modulus value. In accordance with the meaning of reduced time, the actual nonlinear relaxation modulus relates to the linear (infinitesimal strain) modulus as follows: $E_{\text{nonlinear}}(t) = E_{\text{linear}}(t')$. At each time increment, an initial trial value of t' was chosen (based on the previous step) and the calculations were iterated until suitable convergence occurred for t' . A criterion of convergency of 10^{-15} min proved to be fully adequate without requiring excessive computer time. Since the overall time range covered nine decades of logarithmic time, the increments were chosen on a logarithmic basis at 0.05 decade; trials using 0.02 decade showed the same result, so 0.05 decade was considered to be sufficiently close spacing.

An extensive set of calculations was run with a wide range of bulk compliance representations in an attempt to reduce the 0.01, 0.03 and 0.05 strain relaxation curves of Fig. 1 to a single linear (reference state) master curve. The best-fit bulk compliance for all strains is given by $M_0 = 6 \times 10^{-4}/\text{MPa}$, $M_1 = 0.3 \times 10^{-4}/\text{MPa}$, $\tau = 10^6$ min. (This corresponds to a reasonable glassy Poisson's ratio of 0.32 but displays relatively little change of M as it approaches the equilibrium state.) But this solution does not provide a completely unified result when applied to all three data curves. The reduced (zero-strain) results are shown in Fig. 2 along with the zero-strain curve A from Ref. 1.

Although the differences are not large, how are they accounted for? Several procedural differences noticeable in Ref. 1 group around the handling of $M(t)$. The Knauss-Emri equation for $\theta(t)$ in the relaxation case does not include an initial glassy elastic response term $\tau_{11}(0)$. (Since the authors were not able to supply information on computer software used, it is not known how this effect might have been included.) The exponent $(t' - \xi')$ in Eq. (5) was approximated as $(t - \xi)$ in the former work¹; our results show that this factor can be too small by an order of magnitude for some portions of the integration. The approximation could contribute to a solution error.

Fig. 1 Comparison of experiment and computations for relaxation in PVAc at different strain levels (from Ref. 1).

Fig. 2 Best-fit zero-strain relaxation curves from data at 1, 3 and 5% strain.

If one steps outside the theory for the moment and considers the original relaxation data from the standpoint of physical reasoning, a cross-plot of $\log t$ vs. ϵ_0 from Fig. 1 for a series of constant E values shows a reasonable extrapolation of the curves can be made to $\epsilon_0 = 0$. This resulting linearly viscoelastic E does nearly match with the curve A reported previously^{1,4}. Even using this zero-strain curve along with a common bulk characterization, the computerized theory did not produce a satisfactory fit for anything more than the 0.01 (lowest) strain data set; the 0.03 and 0.05 strain curves were significantly far from fitting the experimental data. The implication is that there may be also nonlinearity involved in the bulk modulus behavior at different strain levels (a possibility for PVAc mentioned previously³).

In summary, the present computer solution to the theory fails to produce a unified linear modulus from the nonlinear data given in Fig. 1; correspondingly, starting with the extrapolated zero-strain curve A does not produce the observed results for the nonlinear strain levels. Assuming the original data master curves as correct, then the reasonable extrapolated curve appears not to provide a basis to go back to the nonlinear results. On the other hand, if the data curves turn out to be not an adequate approximation because the time-temperature superposition does not suitably account for nonlinearity (a point on which the authors¹ raise a question), then the theory may call for additional terms and procedures to account for the added nonlinearity.

Perhaps to get the zero-strain curve, it is necessary to have added data on bulk behavior. This preliminary examination shows that the best-fit bulk creep compliance is a relatively high value that actually tends to decrease with time. Is this a manifestation that results from incompleteness in the theory or could it in fact reflect one of the various processes accompanying aging (which always lead to a decrease in volume with time when under constant stress)? These questions do not have clear answers and are offered for discussion.

Constant strain rate results are much less dependent on bulk creep behavior since the times involved are so short (of the order of a minute). Knauss-Emri approximate M in this case as a constant at temperatures close to T_g . Internal comparison of relaxation curves with the constant $\dot{\epsilon}_0$ results indicate different test temperatures for the two sets of data; other property data on PVAc enabled a rough estimate for the reference temperature of Fig. 1 at -13°C (quite far below the listed¹ $T_g = 28^\circ\text{C}$). With the change of temperature ΔT incorporated in Eq. (4), stress results were obtained for $\dot{\epsilon}_0 = 0.01/\text{min}$ and compared in Fig. 3 with the results of Ref. 1. Various values of ΔT as shown produced closest agreement with the previous results¹ using $\Delta T = 20^\circ\text{C}$ (considerably different from the expected $\Delta T = 39.5^\circ\text{C}$ if Fig. 1 corresponded to $T_{\text{ref}} = -13^\circ\text{C}$).

These examples of lack of closure on the theory suggest some aspects of internal consistency may not be fully accounted for. The logic of the theory appears sound given the assumptions; researchers may, however, wish to investigate further the manner in which the free volume contributions are additive.

Fig.-3 Comparison of stress results for constant strain rate. Closest agreement with Ref. 1 obtained by using $\Delta T = +20^\circ\text{C}$ applied to Fig. 1.

THE SHAY-CARUTHERS APPROACH

Shay and Caruthers² propose a model combining a Boltzmann-type superposition integral using a linear viscoelastic Poisson's ratio ν to relate lateral to axial strain and a free volume equation of state. Nonlinearity enters through a volume- and temperature-dependent shifting of the time scale for a relaxing $\nu(t)$. The set of coupled equations to handle the uniaxial extension case is

$$\lambda_l(t) = 1 + \int_{-\infty}^t [\nu(t^* - \xi^*)] \frac{\partial \lambda_a(\xi)}{\partial \xi} d\xi \quad (6)$$

$$\log a(t) = \frac{B}{2.303} \left[\frac{1}{h(t)} - \frac{1}{h_0} \right] \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{\tilde{P}\tilde{V}}{\tilde{T}} = [1 - 2^{-1/6} y(y\tilde{V})^{-1/3}]^{-1} + \frac{2y}{\tilde{T}}(y\tilde{V})^{-2} [1.011(y\tilde{V})^{-2} - 1.2045] \quad (8)$$

where y is fraction of occupied sites, λ_l, λ_a are lateral and axial extension ratio, respectively, $h = 1 - y$ is hole fraction (h_0 is for reference state), B is a material constant, \tilde{P}, \tilde{V} and \tilde{T} are reduced pressure, volume and temperature, respectively. Reduced times t^* and ξ^* are given by Eq. (3). Eq. (7) is the WLF-Doolittle equation and Eq. (8) is the Simha-Somcynsky statistical thermodynamic equilibrium equation of state for the fraction of occupied sites. Equations (6)-(8) must be solved numerically and iteratively for each discrete increment of time over the strain history. Another Boltzmann superposition similar to Eq. (2) then gives the stress history. It should be noted that Eq. (8) is derived for equilibrium conditions. Since processes in polymers below T_g are nonequilibrium in nature, caution is required in evaluating this method.

Shay-Caruthers analyze uniaxial constant strain rate elongation for PMMA material with simplified representation of linear material relaxation spectra, showing variation of stress response with different strain rates and temperatures. Comparisons are purely qualitative as no experimental results are shown. This focuses attention on material representation which proved to be crucial to the analysis. We treat the same loading case but use realistic material representation. The Shay-Caruthers "box" (constant magnitude) distribution of relaxation times for E does not at all approximate the spectrum developed by McLoughlin and Tobolsky⁵, one of their sources of PMMA data; most of their transition curve occurs about six decades later than for a realistic representation. Figure 4 shows a comparison of their result at a constant strain rate of 10^{-2} /sec and $T = 70^\circ\text{C}$ with the present solution of Eq. (6) to (8) using a realistic Prony series representation of the PMMA data.⁵ The stress given by the better material representation is an order of magnitude less than that of the simplified model solution. The analysis suggests that the results of Ref. 2 may be influenced as much by material representation as by the nonlinear method itself. It points to the need in nonlinear analysis of adequate material property data and valid representation of it in the computational procedure.

Fig. 4 Comparison of stress results for constant $\dot{\epsilon}$ with Shay-Caruthers solution.

The Simha-Somcynsky equation (8) did prove to give a time-temperature shift factor between the reference temperature of 115°C and 70°C approximating the results obtainable from Ref. 5. But as T_g is near 110°C for PMMA and the validity of the $\tilde{P}\tilde{V}/\tilde{T}$ relation below T_g has to be questioned, the range of

applicability above and below T_g is not well established. In addition, B in Eq. (7) must be obtained from experimental equilibrium free volume measurements; this usually means data near or above T_g so that B has a limited range of temperature applicability and may need to be considered a function of temperature. Shay-Caruthers have taken note of these limitations and are proposing an alternate theory based on the use of entropy; results of this development have not yet appeared in the literature. They also have a fully nonlinear formulation incorporating in addition a finite strain elasticity tensor. We limit attention here to the "quasi-linear" viscoelastic formulation as it illustrates the principle features of the method and nonlinear viscoelastic behavior may occur at even lower strain levels than does nonlinear elastic response. All forms of the theory need verification as to accuracy by comparison with experimental data.

DISCUSSION

The free volume approaches in theory offer promise of applicability to the thermo-plastic matrix-reinforcement interaction, but several aspects appear to need further development. Since the methods respond strongly to the linear material characterization, further definitive determinations of bulk relaxation modulus are needed for the various materials under study. A correlative property is the Poisson ratio variation with time. These are among the most difficult properties to obtain, but are desirable to fully verify the theories. Further examination of the possible nonlinear behavior in bulk appears called for. Since the constant strain rate check of results is a less rigorous test of a theory, comparisons should be made using stress relaxation behavior into the nonlinear strain regime.

Most of the published comparisons with experimental data to date have been with conditions not far from T_g . Thus, further analysis and testing is desirable to verify the range of temperatures for which the theories are applicable. This is important if a rational approach is to be taken toward understanding the thermal and deformation processing of thermoplastic matrix materials in the manufacture of composites, where deformation beyond the yield point is common.

But what of the engineer faced with the choice of materials or the need to analyze a composite in detail? The methods reviewed certainly do offer qualitative and to some extent quantitative indications of nonlinear behavior as compared with strictly linear viscoelastic analysis. The transition region is moved to shorter times by finite strain; hence, in composite material processing, there is a trend toward an equilibrium modulus more quickly with added straining of the polymer. As higher temperatures also increase the rate of relaxation (creep), there may be the basis here of a quantitative analysis of the synergistic effect of these two factors. As reinforcing fibers offer restraint to matrix deformation in advanced composites, the low but finite strain levels examined in these theories should prove helpful in composite analysis. Since strain tends to speed up the viscoelastic process, the designer may want to choose a material that places the transition zone at longer times to avoid long-term loss of stiffness in the matrix. Although analysts may well be wary of the limitations in temperature range that appear to be present in these methods, the advantage of being able to estimate nonlinear effects by specifying only such quantities as M_g , $E(t)$ and perhaps the interaction coefficients α and B (as in Eq. (4)) makes the methods attractive when all the uncertainties are resolved.

REFERENCES

1. Knauss, W. G. and Emri, I., *Computers and Structures*, 13(1981), 123.
2. Shay, R. M. and Caruthers, J. M., *Journal of Rheology*, 30(1986), 781.
3. McKinney, J. E. and Belcher, H. V., *Journal of Research of the National Bureau of Standards*, 67A(1963), 43.
4. Knauss, W. G. and Emri, I., *Polymer Engineering and Science*, 27(1987), 86.
5. McLoughlin, J. R. and Tobolsky, A. V., *Journal of Colloid Science*, 7(1952), 555.